

LOADABILITY CHARACTERISTICS OF 6-PHASE TRANSMISSION LINE

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the comparative study of the existing 400kV 3-phase double circuit line of GETCO (Gujarat Energy Transmission Company), up-rated to 6-phase with different loading, and voltage rating with respect to line efficiency, regulation and SIL. Discussion made on salient points of Six-phase system, 3-phase double circuit line and HVDC. An assessment of the benefit of HPO lines in performance and operating environment criteria is made with regard to their lower phase order counter-parts. In addition, loadability dependence of HPO lines on Var supply is studied. The findings in present work should be useful in transmission planning and circuit uprating particularly with a HPO option in view.

Keywords: HPOTS; loadability; multi-phase trasmission.

INTRODUCTION

The HVDC transmission and Multiphase power transmission are the emerging two options for addressing the problems with the bulk power transmission over the long distance, out of them the HVDC system is having many advantages like non-synchronous tie, less numbers of conductors required, less losses etc but has substantially higher cost for the terminal equipments, it's inability to transfer reactive power between the two ends, and to change the voltage level is difficult be the major drawbacks which has shadowed its' said advantages and has compelled the research engineers to tailor new policy for the electrical power transmission and to switch over to the another option that is Multiphase power transmission.

The use higher phase order system, with same phase to phase voltage can transfer more power, conversely, maintaining same phase to neutral voltage will decrease phase to phase voltage for the HPO lines means lines can be built with less spacing between the phases, this, reduces the amount of right of way and the tower size to build the HPO line.

We know that the stability requirement, limits the permissible power on EHV lines, which decreases with the increase in line length. The use of Series Capacitors

in long distance transmission lines offers an effective and economical means of improving the stability limits and permits line to carry more power.

Line loadability curves have been a valuable planning tool for the 3-phase systems since their publication by St. Clair ^[1]. An extensive simulation and analysis have revealed that thermal duty, line voltage drop and steady state stability limitations are the main controlling factors for loadability of Short, Medium and Long lines respectively, for the voltages up to 345 KV. As the voltage class increases the terminal system reactances play an important role in determining loadability characteristic of line ^[2]. A significant development in this area makes it possible to incorporate specific operating condition under which a line has to work, identify and determine the overall limitations to power transmission across a line. Further developments ⁽⁴⁾ examine critical dependence of line loadability, on Var supplies incorporating, the effects of load voltage characteristics, distributed nature of line parameters etc. to obtain reactive power constrained loadability limits ⁽⁵⁾.

Amongst the interesting features of HPO transmission, increased power transfer capability and effective utilization of right of way (ROW) are considered to be, the most attractive ones. In order to have a realistic assessment of

power transfer capabilities of these lines, here, the main focus is on plotting the loadability characteristics applying some of the concepts and constraints reported for three phase systems ⁽¹⁻⁵⁾.

Firstly the basic analytical model of the line and the procedure to derive generalized loadability characteristics ⁽²⁾ considering the voltage drop and steady state stability margin limitations are delineated. Finally the loadability dependence on Var supply is studied and loadability consistent with Var supply limits is determined.

THE BASIC CIRCUIT MODEL

The basic circuit model for the loadability analysis, is that of references ^[2,3] adapted for HPO lines represented on single phase basis by positive sequence parameters as shown in Fig : 1.

Fig. 1: A Circuit Model for line loadability study

LOADABILITY DEPENDENCE ON VAR SUPPLY

The St Clair loadability curves and its analytical equivalents imply unlimited Var reserves to maintain voltage at the line terminals. Their applicability therefore hinges largely on Var reserve capability. With $K_s=0$, in Fig:2, it has been shown [4] that the Var limit must be great enough to allow operation at an angular displacement between sending and receiving end voltage of -90° even though the normal operation would be limited to an angle of -44° to ensure 30% stability margin. In situation where Var supply is limited, the loadability limit is decided by voltage stability rather than steady state stability. However the maximum Var capability will largely determine the operating point voltage and stability margin and also it is critical in evaluation of maximum power transfer and critical angular separation.

In the view of above, the maximum value of Var reserve $[Q_m]$ at receiving end bus to ensure acceptable operating point voltage $E_r^0 (>=E_r)$ and stability margin $s.m.0 (>=s.m_{des})$ is determined employing Key's algorithm [4] with

and without series compensation for HPO transmission line. The operating point load Pr^0 , minimum acceptable voltage E_r and desired value of stability margin $s.m_{des}$ are specified. Further no limit is placed on the lower bound, on injected Q.

Fig. 2: Line model of loadability dependence on Var supply

TEST SYSTEM

The construction of the loadability curves and various related issues will now be addressed with the help of existing GETCO's 400 KV three phase double circuit configuration as shown in Fig:3 and loadability curves are constructed for the same configuration when converted in to six phase. Comparative study of the six phase system is made with reference to the three phase double circuit system.

Fig. 3: Geb's Existing 400kv 3-Ph Double Circuit, 10 In. Bundle Spacing Twin Mouse Conductor Used, Dia. 31.77 Mm, 900a C.C./Conductor Height Of Lowest Conductor From Ground: 21.9 M

LINE CONSTANTS AND ASSUMPTIONS:

- Line length : 400 to 1000 Kms
- Operating Voltage : 400 KV
- Type of conductor: Twin mouse
- Bundle spacing : 25 Cms
- Phase spacing : As shown in figure above.
- Height of the lowest conductor from ground: 21.9 M
- Computed line parameters per Km. for 3-ph Double Circuit:
- $L= 0.0005014 \quad C= 2.43 E -8$

Computed line parameters per Km. for 6-ph conversion of the same configuration:

$L = 0.001268 \quad C = 9.01 \text{ E } -9$

- Terminal equipments and machine variants are not considered.
- Shunt compensation specified as susceptance

The table shows the hike in power transfer capability of the existing GEB'S 400 KV line if converted in to the Six-phase. But it can be inferred that the regulation is poorer, compared to the three-phase double circuit line. Further we can see that for the same power to be transferred, the voltage level for six-phase power transmission can be reduced, which reduces the overall tower size and hence, the cost and at the same time mitigate the problems of right of way. The table given below is prepared from the Gujarat Electricity Board's (At present GETCO (Gujarat Energy Transmission Co.)) 400 KV three phase double circuit line data and this configuration when converted in to six phase, it is assumed that the line is cyclically transposed and the line length of 200 Kms is considered.

SALIENT POINTS

From the table we can derive following important points of the High Phase Order Transmission:

- If symmetrical configuration inherently balanced is used , less effect of transposition
- As for six-phase $V_{\text{phase}} = V_{\text{line}}$ as it forms equilateral triangle (Angle = 60).
- For 3-ph double circuit power = $2 \times 3 V_{\text{ph}} I_{\text{ph}} \cos\theta$ Where $V_{\text{phase}} = V_{\text{line}} / \sqrt{3}$
- For 6-ph up rated line power = $6 V_{\text{ph}} I_{\text{ph}} \cos\theta$ Where $V_{\text{phase}} = V_{\text{line}}$
- This fact gives 1.7 to 1.74 times more power than the existing three phase double circuit line depending upon the line configuration.
- For the same power transfer we keep V_{phase} same this will reduce V_{line} so it will reduce the overall dimension of the tower, hence the foundation cost and right of way problem.
- For the same power transfer 6-ph conversion gives better regulation has higher SIL
- For more power transfer if 6-ph conversion is made then it gives poor regulation, but this problem can be well addressed with the available FACTS devices.

GENERALIZED LOADABILITY CURVES

Employing the data as shown in fig:2 and the ratio of power sent to SIL of the existing three phase double circuit Ps/SIL have been computed and plotted against the line lengths between 50 to 600 Kms for the above system.

Graphs show the generalised loadability curves for 400 KV (L-L) three phase, double circuit system, and its conversion to six phase system. The graphs clearly indicates the higher loadability of the HPO i.e. Six phase conversion has the higher loadability compared to the three phase double circuit system.

3-PH DOUBLE CIRCUIT CONFIGURATION									
TYPE	VOLT	IL	REG	EFFI	L	C	SIL	PF	PS IN MW
400 KV GEB'S CONFIG DOUBLE CKT	400	1800	7.38	95.88	5.01E-04	2.43E-08	1112.71	0.9992	1501.78
	400	900	2.98	97.81	5.01E-04	2.43E-08	1112.71	0.9673	736.06
6-PH CIRCUIT CONFIGURATION									
6-PH GEB'S CONFIG	400	1800	8.83	97.60	1.27E-03	9.01E-09	2558.74	0.9771	4426.39
	400	900	2.90	98.76	1.27E-03	9.01E-09	2558.74	0.9974	2187.06
6-PH GEB'S CONFIG	231	1800	22.01	95.92	1.27E-03	9.01E-09	853.36	0.8917	2600.15
	231	900	6.97	97.91	1.27E-03	9.01E-09	853.36	0.9883	1273.73

EFFECT OF TERMINAL SYSTEM IMPEDANCE

The effect of terminal system impedances on line loadability of HPO systems under the same performance criteria (5% voltage drop and 30% stability margin) is studied by varying the terminal system strength between 900A and 7000A. It is observed that the loadability of six phase line shows marked effect as compared to that of three phase lines for short lengths implying that the effect of increase in terminal system strength is to increase loadability of HPO lines.

EFFECT OF SHUNT COMPENSATION

The effect of shunt compensation on loadability is very small. The transmission schemes show an ignorant change in their loadability for a full range of shunt compensation between 0% and 80% at low terminal system impedances. However in case of high terminal impedances the effect of shunt compensation is some what marked.

EFFECT OF SERIES COMPENSATION

Following graphs illustrate, the variation of the loadability of the transmission systems for changes in series compensation between 0% to 80% under the 5% voltage drop and 30% stability margin and a mature terminal systems strength of 1800 A. The effect of, series compensation is considerably high and it more effective, as the phase order increases. Also every additional percent of series compensation yields increasingly greater improvement in line loadability. It is also observed that loadability for short lengths is of higher value and may exceed the thermal ratings of the lines. However this study is only intended to examine the effect of series compensation on loadability of HPO lines without dealing with technical and economical aspects of the problems.

EFFECT OF SHUNT COMPENSATION ON 3-PH DOUBLE CKT AND 6-PH TRANS LINE WITH 5% VOLTAGE REGULATION AND 30% STEADY STATE STABILITY MARGIN

The graph plotted just above shows the effectiveness of series compensation on loadability of the 3-phase Double Circuit GETCO's line configuration. From the graph it is observed that for the lesser line length the loadability limit is higher and as the line length, increases, the loadability

3-PH DOUBLE CKT LINE WITH SERIES COMPENSATION WITH 5% VOLTAGE REGULATION AND 30% STEADY STATE STABILITY MARGIN

limit decreases. With the same line configuration is up-rated with Six-phase transmission mode, in that case the line loadability limit shows a landslide increase in the loadability with respect to its' three-phase counter-part, as shown in the graph given below. Here, the fact underlined above, be the focused point.

QUANTITATIVE BENEFITS WITH HPO OPTION INCLUDING CIRCUIT UPRATING APPLICATION

In order to quantify the additional power transfer with HPO lines, the loadability curves for the two alternative

EFFECT OF SERIES COMP ON 6-PH TRANSMISSION SYSTEM WITH 5% VOLTAGE REGULATION AND 30% STEADY STATE STABILITY MARGIN

systems under the same performance criteria (5% voltage drop and 30% stability margin) and same terminal system impedances are plotted, with sending end power in each case expressed as p.u. of SIL of three phase double circuit line. It can be observed that an additional power transfer capability to the tune of (83 to 71%) in six phase over three

phase is available over the line span considered. It may be noted that these benefits are obtained with the same line structure and same phase-phase voltage in each case. However the ultimate loadability benefits will be modified and dictated by operating criteria in practice.

In order to evaluate the benefit of six phase conversion of a double circuit, three phase (2 x 3 phase) line solely in terms of line loadability, a 400 KV network as in fig: is considered. In uprating the 2 x 3 phase line to six phase line, the adjacent line to line voltages remain the same and also the same conductor currents and power factor are assumed in both modes of operation. The loadability curves of both modes of operations of the lines are shown in graphs. It is seen that an additional power transfer capability of around 75% (Only 73% with no constraints on Er of 5% drop and neglecting the terminal system impedances. It is further verified that the same additional benefit is obtained if the 2 x 3 phase circuit is up rated to $\sqrt{3}$ x 400 KV. Thus the six phase operation is equivalent to a 2 x 3 phase line up rated to $\sqrt{3}$ times its line voltage as far as the loadability is concerned.

CONCLUSION

In this paper the conventional use of the existing three phase double circuit GETCO’s line configuration extended for, Six-phase transmission mode and the comparative loadability study is done leading to the following conclusion:

- 1) If symmetrical configuration inherently balanced is used, less effect of transposition was noticed.
- 2) HPOs have higher inductance and lower capacitance and greater SIL capability keeping in view the following points.
- 3) As for six-phase $V_{phase} = V_{line}$ as it forms equilateral triangle (Angle = 60).
- 4) For 3-ph double circuit power = $2 \times 3 V_{ph} I_{ph} \cos\theta$ Where $V_{phase} = V_{line} / \sqrt{3}$
- 5) For 6-ph up rated line power = $6 V_{ph} I_{ph} \cos\theta$ Where $V_{phase} = V_{line}$
- 6) This fact gives 1.7 to 1.74 times more power than the existing three phase double circuit line depending upon the line configuration.
- 7) For the same power transfer we keep V_{phase} same this will reduce V_{line} so it will reduce the overall dimension of the tower, hence the foundation cost and right of way problem.
- 8) For the same power transfer 6-ph conversion gives better regulation has higher SIL
- 9) For more power transfer if 6-ph conversion is made then it gives poor regulation, but this problem can be well addressed with the available FACTS devices.

- 10) Six phase line offers more power transfer for the same performance criteria (voltage limit and stability margin) as compared to three phase system.
- 11) The shunt compensation has negligible effect on line loadability.
- 12) Six phase line has better voltage performance and better stability margin, especially, during heavy load region compared to their three phase counter-part.
- 13) Six phase up-rating of 2 x 3 phase line yields around 75% benefit in line loadability.
- 14) Series compensation has more pronounce effect on line loadability.
- 15) Compensation required for the same margin of increase in the loadability is less in case of six phase when compared to 2 x 3 phase system, i.e. Var required will be less in six phase system than that in 2 x 3 phase system.

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